

Stability of some Arylhydrazo-5-pyrazolones Chelates with Divalent Iron, Cobalt, Nickel, Copper and Zinc

M. S. RIZK*, H. M. ABDEL-FATTAH, IKHLASS M. ABBASS and Y. M. ISSA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Cairo, Giza, Egypt

Manuscript received 30 June 1992, revised 23 April 1993, accepted 30 April 1993

Pyrazolones are used as analgesics and antipyretics¹ but their most frequent commercial uses are as dyestuffs. Metal chelates of pyrazolones are well known for their analytical and biological uses¹. Snavey and Krecker² determined potentiometrically the relative stabilities of the metal complexes of simple arylazo-5-pyrazolone. The structure-stability relationship of substituted 4-pyrazolone dye chelates with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions has also been reported³. A survey of literature revealed that no work has been done on the chelates of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-4-arylhydrazone-5-pyrazolones. So the present work was undertaken to study the chelation behaviour of these new ligands with some transition metal ions in 70% ethanol medium.

1 ; X = OH

2 ; X = COOH

Results and Discussion

Dissociation constants of the ligands : The \bar{n}_A values were calculated at various pH values from the titration curves. The formation curves relating pH and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values are plotted. The two ionisation constants K_1 and K_2 which correspond to OH and NH groups in 1 and COOH and NH groups in 2 were calculated by the half-integral method⁴. The mean values are listed in Table 1. The data indicate that during complexation, the phenolic

OH group in 1 and the COOH group in 2 dissociate together with NH group.

The high pK values of the carboxylic group can be attributed to the effect of ethanol which can associate very slightly with the charged ionic species contrary to the polar solvents, e.g. water⁵. Moreover, the possible intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these compounds is another factor depressing their dissociation in alcoholic solution.

Stability constants of the complexes : From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values were calculated and plotted against each other resulting in the formation curves of the metal complexes (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Formation curves for Ni, Co, Cu, Zn and Fe complexes with pyrazolone derivative 2 ; $[M^{2+}] = 10^{-3} M$ [pyrazolone 2] = $10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 0.1 M$.

The \bar{n} values extend to 2.0 indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes. The overall

stability constants ($\log \beta$) were calculated using the methods described earlier⁴ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—MEAN VALUES OF $\log \beta_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ OF THE METAL CHELATES WITH THE PYRAZOLONES (1 AND 2)

Medium : 70% (v/v) ethanol-water, temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 M$

M(II) ion	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
Pyrazolone 1 :		
	7.70 (OH)	
H ⁺	10.70 (NH)	
Fe	13.89	25.40
Co	12.11	21.22
Ni	11.00	19.20
Cu	10.73	18.21
Zn	10.08	15.86
Pyrazolone 2 :		
	7.50 (COOH)	
H ⁺	10.75 (NH)	
Fe	20.04	33.04
Co	11.95	21.95
Ni	11.03	19.12
Cu	16.45	24.65
Zn	8.05	16.10

The stability constants ($\log \beta_1$) increase in the order, Fe > Co > Ni > Zn with pyrazolone 1 and Fe > Co > Ni < Cu > Zn with pyrazolone 2, which may be discussed theoretically. A theoretical explanation of this order can be assumed considering the ionic radii of the metal ions regardless of their different coordination numbers and their complex structure.

However, a simple interpretation of the stability order is rather complicated by other considerations such as the relative stabilities which depend on the aquo-complexes in which the H₂O molecules are replaced by the ligands in aqueous medium. However, the abnormal high stability of Fe^{II}-pyrazolone complex may be attributed to the known orbital stabilisation which occurs in Fe^{II} ion during the complex formation⁶.

Experimental

The ligands (1 and 2; m.p. 231 and 254° respectively) were prepared by coupling of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone in aqueous NaOH and NaOAc medium with diazonium salts of the

corresponding amines⁷. The crude products were crystallised from dioxane or acetic acid. The metal chloride (A.R.) and their solutions (10⁻³M) were prepared and standardised using the recommended methods⁸.

The pH-potentiometric titrations of the pyrazolones (1 and 2) and their complexes were carried out with NaOH solution using a Chintrex 62 pH-meter at 25° and 0.1 M ionic strength. A 1 M sodium chloride solution was used to control the ionic strength during the titrations. In all cases 70% ethanol-water medium was used to avoid the precipitation of organic ligands and their complexes as well. The pH values in this medium were corrected (± 0.25 pH unit) according to Bates⁹. The following three mixtures were prepared¹⁰: (i) HCl + NaCl, (ii) HCl + NaCl + ligand and (iii) HCl + NaCl + ligand + metal ion. Each mixture was titrated against standard 0.196 M NaOH solution using a combined glass electrode calibrated by standard buffers. The average number of protons (\bar{n}_A) associated with the ligand molecule at different pH values, the average number of ligands (\bar{n}) attached to a metal ion and the free ligand exponent (pL) were all calculated using the equation given by Sarin and Munshi¹¹. The methods used for calculating the stepwise stability constants were (a) interpolation at half \bar{n} value, (b) correction term method, (c) successive approximation method, and (d) mid-point method.

References

1. C. P. SINGH and A. C. OJHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1172 ; D. M. CZAKIS-SULIKOWSKA, B. KUZNIK and A. MALINOWSKA, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1990, **121**, 585.
2. F. A. SNAVELY and B. D. KRECKER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **81**, 4199.
3. A. E. HILALY, A. S. SHAWALI and M. A. MADKOUR, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1979, **36**, 179.
4. H. IRVING and H. A. ROSSOTTI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 581.
5. A. COVINGTON, "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", Plenum, London, 1973 ; N. S. ISAACS, "Physical Organic Chemistry", Longman, London, 1990.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.

NOTE

- 7 F A SNAVELY, W S TRAHANOUSKY and F H SUYDAM, *J Org Chem*, 1962, **27**, 994
- 8 A I VOLGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", 2nd ed, Longmans, London, 1962
- 9 R G BATES, P MAYA and R A ROBINSON, *J Phys Chem*, 1963, **67**, 1833
- 10 N T ABEL-GHANI, A L EL-ANSARY and A A SALEM, *Thermochim Acta*, 1987, **122**, 231
- 11 R SARIN and K N MUNSHI, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1972, **34**, 581

